

interstore

D3.4 – Report on Test and validate in laboratory environment

WP3 – HESS Dimensioning, Integration and Verification of Developed Software Tools

T3.4 – Test and validate in laboratory environment

Submission date: 31.12.2025

Project Acronym	INTERSTORE
Call	HORIZON-CL5-2022-D3-01
Grant Agreement N°	101096511
Project Start Date	01-01-2023
Project End Date	31-12-2025
Duration	36 months

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101096511. Disclaimer: The sole responsibility for any error or omissions lies with the editor. The content does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Commission. The European Commission is also not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained herein.

INFORMATION

Written By	Elyas Rakhshani (HES),	2025-11-28
	Nithin Manuel (RWTH)	2025-11-28
	Alessandra Martino (ENX)	2025-11-28
Checked by	Elyas Rakhshani (HES)	2025-11-16
Reviewed by	Elyas Rakhshani (HES)	2025-12-08
	Erdem Gumrukcu (ENX)	2025-12-08
Approved by	Antonello Monti (RWTH) – Project Coordinator	2025-12-19
	Alexandre Lucas (INESCTEC)	2025-12-19
Status	Full document	2025-12-19

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

CO	Confidential	
CL	Classified	
PU	Public	x

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

VERSIONS

Date	Version	Author	Comment
30-01-2025	0.1	Nithin Manuel (RWTH)	ToC - draft
01-08-2025	0.2	Nithin Manuel (RWTH)	Initial content per section
01-11-2025	0.3	Nithin Manuel (RWTH)	Section 2 added
20-11-2025	0.4	Elyas Rakhshani (HES)	Section 3 updated
23-11-2025	0.5	Nithin Manuel (RWTH)	Section 4 Added
27-11-2025	0.6	Alessandra Martino (ENX)	Section 3 Updated
28-11-2025	0.7	Nithin Manuel (RWTH)	Section 5 Added
02-12-2025	0.8	Nithin Manuel (RWTH)	Section 5 Updated
03-12-2025	0.9	Elyas Rakhshani (HES)	Section 5 Updated
04-12-2025	1.0	Nithin Manuel (RWTH)	Full version for review

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

InterSTORE is an EU-funded project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Research and Innovation Programme under Grant Agreement N. 101096511.

DISCLAIMER

The sole responsibility for the content of this report lies with the authors. It does not necessarily reflect the opinion of the European Union. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

While this publication has been prepared with care, the authors and their employers provide no warranty with regards to the content and shall not be liable for any direct, incidental or consequential damages that may result from the use of the information, or the data contained therein.

ABBREVIATIONS AND ACRONYMS

API	Application Programming Interface
AWS	Amazon Web Services
BAP	Basic Application Profile
BAIOP	Basic Application Interoperable Profile
BMS	Battery Management System
BESS	Battery Energy Storage System
CA	Certificate Authority
CAN BUS	Controller Area Network bus
CHIL	Control Hardware In Loop
CSIP	Common Smart Inverter Profile
DCAP	Device Capability
DEMS	Distributed Energy Management System
DER	Distributed Energy Resources
DES	Distributed Energy System
DNS	Domain Name Service
DERMS	Distributed Energy Resources Management System
EMS	Energy Management System
EUT	Equipment Under Test
FSA	Function Set Assignment

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

GUI	Graphical User Interface
HESS	Hybrid Energy Storage System
HIL	Hardware In the Loop
HEMS	Hybrid Energy Management System
HyDEMS	Hybrid Distributed Energy Management System
IOP	Interoperability Profile
IP	Internet Protocol
IT	Information Technology
JRC	Joint Research Center
JRC-SGILab	Joint Research Center-Smart Grid Interoperability
JSON	JavaScript Object Notation
LFDI	Long Form Device Identifier
MICS	Model Implementation Conformance Statement
NATS	Neural Autonomic Transport System
PICS	Protocol Implementation Conformance Statement
PIXIT	Protocol Implementation Extra Information for Testing
REST	Representational State Transfer
REF-Client	Reference Client
REF-Server	Reference Server
RTDS	Real Time Digital Simulator
SFDI	Short Form Device Identifier
SG	Smart Grid
SoC	State of the Charge
SoF	State of the Function
SoH	State of the Health
SOA	State-of-the-Art

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

SUT	System Under test
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
TCP	Transmission Control Protocol
UC	Use Case
UDP	User Datagram Protocol
UML	Unified Modelling Language
XML	Extensible Markup Language
YAML	Yet Another Markup Language

TABLE OF CONTENTS

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY.....	10
1 Introduction.....	11
1.1 Background.....	11
1.2 Objectives of the report.....	12
2 Interoperability Testing Methodology	12
2.1 Introduction to interoperable testing methodology.....	12
2.2 Use Case Creation.....	13
2.3 Basic Application Profiles.....	14
2.4 Basic Application Interoperability Profiles	14
3 Development of Interoperable Profiles Based on Software Tools.....	15
3.1. Adopted Testbench with LPC in RWTH Laboratory.....	15
3.1.1 Description of Use Case with components	16
3.1.2 Energy Management System	18
3.1.3 Legacy Protocol Converter.....	18
3.1.4 VILLAS NODE.....	19
3.1.5 RTDS Simulator	19
3.1.6 Identification of Interoperability Profiles	19
3.2 Adopted Test bench with LPC in HESS Tec Laboratory.....	23
3.3 Adopted Test Bench with Testing Tool to Validate IEEE 2030.5 in Enel X Laboratory ...	27
3.3.1 Description of Test Cases as per Standard.....	27
4 Configuration of Interoperability Profiles	33
4.1 Adopted Configuration for Basic Application Interoperability Profile with LPC in RWTH Laboratory.....	33
4.1.1 Configuration of RTDS to VILLAS NODE.....	33

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

4.1.2 Configuration of To and from of LPC	35
4.1.3 Configuration of EMS to LPC.....	40
4.2 Adopted Configuration for Basic Application Interoperability Profile with LPC in HESS Tech Laboratory.....	45
4.2.1 Overview of Configuration	45
4.2.2 Communication Architecture and Mapping	46
4.3 Adopted Configuration with Testing Tool to Validate IEEE 2030.5 in Enel X Laboratory	47
4.3.1 Device Configuration	48
4.3.2 Testing tool configuration	49
5 Test Results	53
5.1 Test Results Basic Application Interoperability Profile with LPC in RWTH Laboratory	53
5.2 Test Result of LPC in HESS Tech Laboratory	55
5.2.1 Virtual Inertia Response to a Frequency Event	56
5.2.2 KPI Evaluation for UC4.....	58
5.2.4 Comparison: LPC-Based Integration vs. CAN-Based Approach	59
5.2.5 Summary	59
5.3 Test Result of Testing Tool in Enel X Tech Laboratory	59
6 CONCLUSION	62
7 REFERENCES	63
8 LIST OF TABLES.....	65
9 LIST OF FIGURES.....	66

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable, D3.4 – Report on the Test and validate on Laboratory Environment, documents the work carried out in Task T3.4 of the InterSTORE project, which focuses on the validation and testing procedure to showcase interoperability and native testing software tools across multiple laboratories from both academic and industrial partners in the projects. Building on the developments from WP2, where the native IEEE 2030.5 testing tool and the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) were designed and validated, this task translates those solutions into real-world use cases carried out in labs level. The objective is to validate and test both power hardware in the loop and control hardware in loop with ancillary services in legacy and native systems with same LPC and native IEEE 2030.5 which overcoming the limitations of proprietary or legacy protocols while ensuring compliance with modern interoperability standards.

The report addresses the ways to construct the interoperability testing profiles, with a particular emphasis on the LPC and native testing on IEEE 2030.5 supported device. The LPC, operating as an external protocol translator, allows existing assets using protocols such as Modbus or MQTT to participate in an IEEE 2030.5-based control ecosystem over the NATS messaging backbone. Meanwhile the testing software consists of native IEEE 2030.5 server constructed to be a part of the testing tool to hold the IEEE 2030.5 resources.

Section 2 provides the need of a scientific research to identify the best interoperable scenario among the possible choices, the Smart Grid interoperability testing methodology outlines the optimised way to develop an interoperable profile on given use case. Section 3 describes the step-by-step way to create the interoperability profile with various actors in the experiment all actors in the experiment and the architecture is explained in detail to comprehend enough of the chosen interoperability scenario. Section 4 is addresses the adopted configuration for each interoperability scenarios that evaluate independently in different labs. There is a common configuration can be derived based on the LPC that can be used in different experiments. The Section 5 delivers the results of the conducted experiments in the labs and validate that the expected outcomes are qualified as per the norms of the use case and conformance tests of the IEEE 2030.5 is verified.

The work reported here demonstrates the versatility, extensibility and resilience of the interoperable tools developed in InterSTORE. The innovative grid services need to test and validate in the laboratory conditions with developed interoperable solutions will pave the way for deploying in pilots' studies and a stepping stone to develop the commercial solutions. Furthermore, the approach that proposed to choose the interoperability scenario based on the IEEE 2030.5 is replicable to other solutions where the interoperability conditions have to formulate with IEEE 2003.5. Last but not least it's one of the first approach in the EU to test the IEEE 2030.5 native Distributed Energy Resource with developed testing tool and procedure and this tool and procedure is accepted and appreciated by the IEEE 2030.5 standard SunSpec Alliance.

1 Introduction

The InterSTORE project involves creating software tools and validating them through laboratory testing to achieve the interoperability a stepping stone for the pilots to achieve the desirable results. Task 3.4 lead by RWTH to formulate the best interoperable conditions based on the proven studies such as JRC smart Grid Interoperable Methodology. This focus on to make sure that laboratory infrastructure is well equipped to realize the created use case, this is accomplished by the previous developments from the WP2, where legacy protocol converter(LPC), testing procedure and software tool were designed to bridge gap between the modern and legacy system, the testing tool is meant to test native IEEE 2030.5 protocol which is center stage of the InterSTORE project offers interoperability.

1.1 Background

This is the age where the power systems getting smart through the emergence of new generation of smart grids, driven increasing renewables adoption and the integration diverse energy domains. This development creates space for DER's such as photovoltaic systems , hybrid battery storage systems, EV charging stations, and flexible loads. As the power system expands, an increasing number of actors adopt diverse communication protocols, introducing substantial interoperability challenges for utility platforms and EMS. These systems must continue to perform critical control functions without being affected by communication delays The IEEE 2030.5 standard provides a comprehensive, service-oriented communication framework for DER integration, while NATS offers a lightweight, low-latency messaging backbone suitable for distributed control scenarios.

There is clear need for an Interoperable tool that can facilitate the communication between different actors for this reason in the InterSTORE WP2 partners developed software-based solutions. Those are Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) which maps from MQTT or Modbus to IEEE 2030.5, allowing that utility platforms only need to operate in IEEE 2030.5. This comes with without modifying the existing device firmware thanks to its platform agnostic and modularity. There is also another software tool, known as the testing tool and procedure, designed to test IEEE 2030.5 natively. This tool is unique in that it includes a fully integrated IEEE 2030.5 server, which is essential for adding and managing protocol resources during testing, since the process requires client-server interaction. The client used in the test is a device that natively supports IEEE 2030.5.

Task T3.4 builds upon to tests and validate the software solutions made for interoperability and native IEEE 2003.5 integration. This task includes the independent works of 3 different laboratories in 3 different countries based on the particular use case scenario. The testing formulated based on the Smart Grid Interoperability testing methodology by JRC-SGILab. JRC-SGILab is the Smart Grids Innovation Lab of the European Commission's Joint Research Centre, providing a controlled environment to test, validate, and evaluate smart grid technologies. The organization supports research, interoperability studies.

1.2 Objectives of the report

The purpose of this deliverable (D3.4) is to document the testing and validation of the interoperability and testing software tools developed in WP2 with the selected partner laboratories, detailing the chosen testing strategies, implementation steps, and results. The report serves three main objectives:

1. To define and document laboratory-specific testing strategies – detailing how each partner has adapted the IEEE 2030.5 testing tool or LPC to its laboratory infrastructure without adding or altering existing tools and software's.
2. To present how to make an interoperable testing procedure and validation – by providing a way to make a methodology to formulate interoperable testing scenario and how can draw scenarios used with LPC and testing tool is straight forward plug and play how to operate it
3. To provide benchmarked outcomes for control hardware in the loop – The results of the experiments in the labs validates that the outcomes are in the allowable range this proves that this experiment is capable of adapting to fast control services in the smart grid.

By achieving these objectives, the report contributes to InterSTORE's goal of testing and validation methods provides valuable insights for replication in future projects and for stakeholders aiming to adopt similar interoperability frameworks.

The following sections of this report are structured as follows: Section 2 introduces briefly the interoperability testing methodology, focusing on the Smart Grid Interoperability Methodology a framework developed by the JRC-SGI lab. Section 3 offers development of the Interoperable profiles based on the developed software tools from WP2. Section 4 presents configurations that apt for the chosen interoperable scenarios. Finally, Section 5 presents the outcomes of the laboratory experiment.

2 Interoperability Testing Methodology

In the InterStore project developed software tools facilitate and improve the interoperability of the smart grid. The software tools developed in WP2 of InterStore is purely based on novel IEEE 2030.5 standard combined with NATS a fast-messaging protocol. Since the interoperability is the focus of developed software tools there is need to use standard smart grid interoperability testing methodologies to prove and validate the software tools seamless integrate with field devices, protocol converters, simulators, platforms, EMS. There is well known interoperable testing methodology proposed by JRC-SGILab.

2.1 Introduction to interoperable testing methodology

The “Smart Grid interoperability testing methodology” from JRC-SGILab presents best practices for UC developers, experimenters and analysts to perform an integrated Interoperability testing in SG applications [1]. The step-by-step procedure suggested by the JRC-SGILab is schematically depicted in Figure 1.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

Figure 1 Block diagram of EC-JRC-SGILP propose methodology for Interoperability test

The interoperability testing methodology begins with UC development that outlines potential interaction sequences among the actors and components within the system for a defined functionality. The UC serves to systematically document both functional and non-functional requirements and establish the groundwork for test design and test bed setup. The Profiling phase consists of creating Basic Application Profile (BAP) and Basic Application Interoperable Profile (BAIOP). BAP definitions require identifying the applicable standard suites and the specific options taken from those standards to determine their implementation approach to fulfil the intended UC functionality. The BAP definition process specifically addresses the standards and options mandates the information exchanges between UC actors and components, including alternative interaction pathways. Given that standards may offer various options, multiple BAPs can characterise each actor interface. Following complete BAP specification across all interfaces, BAIOPs are then developed to outline Interoperability profile (IOP) test execution procedures under different conditions subjected to scope of the interest. Each BAIOP comprises of a unique BAP combination, that covers the given UC. This comprehensive BAIOP set subsequently serves as the basis for formulating experimental test cases that verify proper interoperability support for the described UC functions.

2.2 Use Case Creation

Since the Use case revolve around the smart grid these Use Cases must thoroughly address and clearly define interoperability among actors, systems, subsystems and components. Use Cases form the foundation for defining the functional and non-functional requirements, as well as developing test cases, test profiles, and procedures for both conformance and interoperability testing [2]. Moreover, they guide the design of testing experiments and test bed configurations. Use cases facilitate shared comprehension across various sectors, committees, and stakeholders involved in intricate systems like smart grid. UCs can be presented informally through text documents accompanied by illustrations, or more formally using Use Case Diagrams as defined in the Unified Modelling Language (UML), which is the recommended approach. Depending on the nature the use case can be classified as Business UC and Technical or System UC. The former describes business processes that the system actors should perform. Later will describes about the smart grid functions to be executed in the business use case. In the perspective of this deliverables and InterStore the use cases

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

entitled to carry out in the laboratory based on the availability of the test's beds and on the interoperability testing methodology and later adopt it for the pilots.

2.3 Basic Application Profiles

Users (such as utilities, grid operators, energy services providers, user groups, and others) are generally required to create detailed specifications that outline how specific standards, or standard sets will be implemented. These specifications must identify which optional elements from the standards will be utilized and describe their application methods to realize the functionality defined in the use case. This profiling phase is referred to as the BAP. As a first step in defining the Use Case's Basic Application Profile, one must analyse information flows among actors. These flows consist of information exchanges occurring between pairs of actors. Two actors are deemed to interact when they exchange information at least once during the UC.

Each information flow requires verification of possible alternative interaction methods between the two actors involved. Alternative methods involve information exchange routed through one or more intermediary actors. This makes it essential for the UC description to be detailed and inclusive of all potential actors, interactions, and alternative communication channels. A well-crafted and complete UC description supports efficient profiling and reduces the likelihood of missing interactions that could later threaten system interoperability.

2.4 Basic Application Interoperability Profiles

Basic Interoperability profile is a test specification document created during the testing phase that expands upon the Basic Application profile. The difference between the Basic Application profile and Interoperability profile is that former is formulated in the design phase and the later, is designed during the testing phase. The purpose of the BAIOP is to verify that actors can communicate with each other to perform specific functionalities by testing all possible communication methods and combinations. BAIOP expands upon BAP by incorporating several critical elements necessary for comprehensive testing. These additions include device configuration specifications, test configuration details along with the communication infrastructure topology, BAP-related test cases, specific capability descriptions such as Protocol Implementation Conformance Statement (PICS), Protocol Implementation extra Information for Testing (PIXIT), and Model Implementation Conformance Statement (MICS) in the case of IEC 61850, as well as an engineering framework that addresses both data modelling instances and communication infrastructure aspects including topology and communication service mapping. Moreover, its implementation specific based on the standard not the device specific. It tests whether the equipment under test can properly execute specific functionality as defined in the Basic Application Profile and integrate correctly within the system. The BAIOP follows a structured format that includes seven main components: an identifier and description section, BAP identifiers, Use Case identifier, referenced documents, terms, definitions and abbreviations, functionality and scope definition, and a comprehensive testing process description. The testing process description section is particularly detailed, encompassing four critical parts that establish the foundation for thorough interoperability assessment. These four parts consist of evaluation criteria that define interoperability standards and expected Equipment Under Test (EUT) behaviour, EUT specifications covering both technical and operational requirements, a System Under Test (SUT) description that details the configuration, Test Bed setup, devices, and infrastructure, and test configuration specifications that outline measurement points, data collection methods, and interface requirements. The goal of this structured approach is to produce clear and unambiguous pass/fail verdicts for interoperability testing.

3 Development of Interoperable Profiles Based on Software Tools

The software tools developed in the WP2 must be used in the interoperable scenarios where different kind of actors connected to achieve a common goal. There are 3 tools mainly developed in the WP2:

- a native client/server library of IEEE 2030.5
- the legacy protocol converter that converts between legacy protocol such as Modbus and MQTT to IEEE 2030.5 and sends it via NATS last
- a testing software to test native IEEE 2030.5 supported devices, the tests are conformance tests to validate that the device under test is expected to have all the functionalities of IEEE 2030.5 standard.

To validate the InterSTROE solutions it is necessary to create an interoperability profile between software tools and laboratory infrastructure. The laboratory facilities are meant to work with specifically designed use case scenarios. The laboratory in the RWTH is focused on the load shedding use case through the hardware in the loop experiment system with an RTDS simulator. In this setting, the legacy protocol converter was tested. Second laboratory is in HESS tech grid lab Valencia to test innovative fast frequency service virtual inertia and it's a power hardware in the loop, the legacy protocol converter from the WP2 is part of virtual inertia testing. The third testbed is very special and novel in European context the native IEEE 2030.5 conformance testing and validation is carried out in the Enel X laboratory in Italy and the tool is used is the testing software developed in WP2.3. The methodology to carry out use cases validation and testing in laboratory environment is as per JRC Interoperable testing methodology, in this chapter describes the formulation of the testing and validation based on the Interoperability framework.

3.1. Adopted Testbench with LPC in RWTH Laboratory

The Hardware-in-the-Loop (HIL) test bench shown in Figure 2 assesses the interoperability of our selected use case. It combines models of electrical communication networks with the actors involved in the scenario, creating a realistic environment where grid components and participants can interact to demonstrate load shedding as a fast frequency service [3].

Figure 2 Test bed set up adopted based on use case in RWTH laboratory

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

More specifically, Control Hardware in Loop (CHIL) is selected as HIL system with RS CAD modelling environment to model the power grid in Figure 3. The low voltage microgrid incorporates a slight modified version of the Banshee microgrid. The adjustable small-scale industrial setup is backed by three utility radial feeders. The feeders have a limited connectivity through switches, each eligible to carry its critical load. The total electricity demand varies from 5 MW to 14 MW for the minimum and maximum loads. The system ratings include medium voltages of 4.16 kV and 13.8 kV, and low voltages of 208 V and 480 V. There are around 18 aggregated loads supplied by the feeders. The modelled Banshee microgrid is interfaced with the RTDS simulator via GT NETx2 card. For the communication network from the ethernet link is used to connect the switch via UDP/TCP from the Ethernet switch the communication goes through ethernet and in the server runs the entire tech stack which is available via browser for monitor and control. The detailed tech stack will be depicted in the following description of use case.

Figure 3 Banshee microgrid modelled in RSCAD

3.1.1 Description of Use Case with components

The UC focuses on load shedding to assess one of the rapid frequency services provided by the proposed platform. The scenario begins by isolating a specific grid region into islanding mode and tripping its feeder circuit breaker. This triggers a frequency decline in the area. When frequency reaches the 49.5 Hz threshold, the load shedding algorithm activates, disconnecting the largest load and restoring frequency to within acceptable limits. The action that triggers from the user-controlled EMS reaches the grid running in the simulator through different actors as depicted in Figure 4 (connect to the interoperability chain). The chain of actors starts as EMS \leftrightarrow LPC, LPC \leftrightarrow VILLAS Node and VILLAS Node \leftrightarrow RTDS, where EMS, LPC, VILLAS mutually interact to provide the grid the frequency restoration which happens as result of the virtual islanding operation in the grid by virtue of tripping the circuit

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

breaker permitting the grid to operate itself to attain the frequency restoration can be achieved by load shedding. To mitigate the frequency drop condition the actor in the chain has to act as fast as possible within the limit of milliseconds ranges to establish practical uninterrupted operation of the islanded microgrid. The most vital part while developing and designing the use case it's necessary to describe the profile each actor's involved in the chain. While describing the use cases it's important to underline the protocols involved in the communication channel from end to end. Since the interoperable systems often work with various protocols, in this case of interest in InterStore the IEEE2030.5 is the interoperability link because of its rich syntax facilities to map from legacy protocols such as Modbus, MQTT makes it as favourite choice to interoperate with modern EMS, platforms. Not only that the xml syntax of IEEE 2030.5 offers its easy conversion to most common web-oriented JSON payloads that can be used via message publishing systems such as NATS, which indeed used as part of the protocol translation to carry out the part of the communication. To wrap up the use case formulation it's the carefully chosen hardware and software's to achieve the interoperability with minimum latency and depicting that multi-disciplinary software's from different actors works seamless to achieve the desired output.

Figure 4 Test bed set up adopted based on use case in RWTH laboratory

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

Frequency Over Time

Figure 5 Energy Management Systems GUI

3.1.2 Energy Management System

The EMS is the face of the entire tech stack in IT systems terms named as the front end of the application and it comes with a graphical user interface, this GUI is running on any web browser. The GUI permit the user to trigger the experimental control event load shedding when the button got clicked the actions will pass through the chain where all other actors propagate the event. There is another part to monitor the frequency of the grid this indicates that the grid is in the stable state or unstable state, it's a real time update of the grid frequency shown in figure 5 it's a real time vs frequency plot update continuously. The other measurement that calculates behind the scenes is recovery time after the control event triggered from the GUI, the recovery time indicates in terms of latency is a metric of the interoperable actors in the chain to discover how good it's and does it meet the industrial standards. The red line represents the critical Threshold value of the frequency and if the frequency goes below this value the grid entering in the unstable situation, this occurred after triggering the Grid Islanding Mode button. The blue line with dots stands for the stable operating frequency of the grid.

3.1.3 Legacy Protocol Converter

The Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) is one protocol converter that converts the message from MQTT and Modbus into corresponding IEEE 2030.5 messages this conversion based on the configuration within the LPC and LPC will run as standby tool it's easy integrated into docker compose by the available docker image of LPC. The message arrives via MQTT can be xml or JSON that will be converted into IEEE 2030.5 which message structure is xml, this xml data will publish via NATS to the WebSocket endpoints, since most of the browsers they only support WebSocket protocol for the real-time data acquisition and streaming. The most important part of this actor is to make sure that the transitions and message translations run as fast as possible without falling apart [4].

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

3.1.4 VILLAS NODE

VILLAS node is a protocol converter that works directly with simulators, the simulator in the RWTH laboratory is connected via VILLAS Node it's a well know open-sourced software for converting between different protocols. Mostly the simulators send UDP and TCP data packets. The VILLAS node captures UDP packets and converts them into corresponding MQTT messages with JSON as the payload. It is referred to as a 'node' because VILLAS framework software contains multiple node types (socket nodes, MQTT nodes, database nodes, etc.), and in this use case, it is specifically the MQTT node that handles the protocol conversion and data formatting. Most important abilities of VILLAS are that it works with many protocols each node in villas is node that operate with a particular protocol this makes the villas as first choice to interoperate with LPC which is developed in the InterStore. Multiple protocol converters can have connected each other and operates independently to achieve the industrial desirable outcomes

3.1.5 RTDS Simulator

The RTDS simulator is where the banshee microgrid is simulating in the NovaCor of RTDS and there is a GT net card associated to facilitate the communication from RTDS to a server where the VILLAS NODE is deployed to receive the UDP data packets [5]. The RS CAD software is the native software of RTDS to design the banshee microgrid and it can start the simulation. The RTDS simulator emulates the industrial standard conditions, allowing engineers to test real protection and control devices in a closed-loop environment before deployment to operational microgrids, thereby validating system behaviour and de-risking critical failures in actual power systems.

3.1.6 Identification of Interoperability Profiles

In the use case description, its mentioned about the actors participating in the chain to properly formulate the profiling phase through an analysis of the interactions between the actors needed. The message sequence chart illustrates in 6 shows the interactions between 3 UC actors [6].

Figure 6 Message Sequence chart representing the interaction between the UC actors

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

The specification of the information flows and the virtual islanding mechanism is described in Table 1, where the use case step-by-step analysis is shown. In the examined use case, the Simulation RTDS continuously operates at a stable frequency level of the simulated microgrid in grid-connected mode and transmits real-time frequency measurements to the EMS for continuous situational awareness (step 1). Upon operator initiation through the user interface button in the EMS, the EMS issues a command to the LPC to transition the microgrid to islanded operation via combination two protocols WebSocket/http and NATS/REST (step 2). LPC converts it to an IEEE 2030.5 standardized payload message, forwarding it to VILLAS (step 3). VILLAS processes the activation signal and sends the islanding command to the RTDS, instructing it to trip the circuit breaker at the point of common coupling and transition the microgrid to autonomous operation. The RTDS executes the islanding operation by opening the breaker, and the simulated microgrid immediately enters islanded mode, causing the frequency to deviate rapidly due to the loss of grid support. The RTDS transmits the frequency measurement back to the VILLAS (step 5). The VILLAS receives the UDP/TCP payload and convert it to MQTT/Modbus Json payload and send to the LPC (step6). The LPC convert the Json payload from MQTT [7] to IEEE 2030.5 xml and send it via NATS/REST (step 7). NATS/REST carries the IEEE 2030.5 xml payload transfer it to WebSocket [8] which enters the EMS with intelligent control algorithms analyses the frequency measurement in real-time and recognizes that the microgrid has transitioned to islanded mode. Based on these intelligent control techniques and without requiring explicit user intervention, the EMS automatically determines the required load shedding command and issues a Load Shedding Command to the LPC (repeats the steps from 1 to 4). The LPC receives this command and converts it from MQTT/Modbus to an IEEE 2030.5 standardized payload message containing the load reduction command, forwarding it to VILLAS. VILLAS receives the load shedding directive and dispatches it to the Simulation RTDS, instructing the simulated loads to reduce their consumption proportionally to restore frequency balance. The RTDS executes the load shedding operation within the simulated microgrid, and the frequency begins to stabilize as generation and reduced load reach equilibrium. The performance of the entire islanding and frequency restoration process is validated through continuous real-time monitoring of system parameters by the EMS, ensuring successful transition to stable autonomous operation under an integrated energy management perspective with autonomous decision-making capabilities.

Table 1 Step by Step Analysis of Use Case 1

Step No	Event	Description of Process	Information Producer	Information Receiver	Information Exchanged
1	RTDS base-line frequency operation and transmission	Simulation RTDS operates at a stable frequency in simulated microgrid a grid connected mode and send real time frequency to EMS	RTDS Processing Unit	EMS	Stable grid frequency data along with the real time of operating in UDP/TCP

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

2	Operator Trigger islanding Mode	By clicking the Islanding mode EMS issues the islanding mode command to LPC	EMS GUI	LPC	Islanding mode activation command send via Websocket /http and NATS/REST the data format is json and xml
3	Protocol Conversion	Converts the Islanding command to IEEE 2030.5 standard	LPC	VILLAS	IEEE 2030.5 message arrives in VILLAS via MQTT/Modbus jsonpayload
5	Microgrid activate the island mode	The banshee microgrid activates the islanding mode put the grid in unstable situation frequency drops	RTDS	VILLAS	Islanded frequency send via UDP/TCP to VILLAS
6	Protocol Conversion	The dropped frequency reaches VILLAS and send to LPC	VILLAS	LPC	Converts the UDP/TCP message into MQTT/Modbus payload in json structure
7	EMS activates Load shedding command	EMS evaluates the received frequency in every epoch and it's control algorithms works instantly to stabilise the grid	LPC	EMS	Before websockets /http sending to the GUI the algorithm triggered so NATS/REST message from LPC take actions

From the above table and schematic diagram, it's easy to identify the Basic Application Profiles (BAPs), the BAPs are built based on the interfaces between all the different actors involved in the UC. As depicted in figure 5 the interaction links of interest are the interfaces

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

EMS<->LPC, LPC<->VILLAS and VILLAS<->RTDS. The list of the considered BAPs related to the interfaces between 3 actors is shown in the table 2

Table 2 List of the BAPs considered for the selected UC

From Actor	To Actor	Technology	BAP Identifier
RTDS	VILLAS	UDP	BAP1.1
		TCP	BAP1.2
VILLAS	LPC	MQTT	BAP2.1
		Modbus	BAP2.2
LPC	EMS	NATS	BAP3.1
		REST	BAP3.2
EMS	LPC	Web Socket	BAP4.1
		Https	BAP4.2

Among the above BAPs definitions, the next step to form the possible Basic Application Interoperability Profiles (BAIOPs), the BAIPOs will determine which technologies works along with each other. The table 3 lists some of BAIOPs

Table 3 List of some BAIOPs

BAP	BAIOP 1	BAIOP 2	BAIOP 3	BAIOP 4	BAIOP 5	BAIOP 6	BAIOP 7	BAIOP 8	BAIOP 9
BAP1.1	*	*			*	*	*	*	
BAP1.2			*	*					*

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

BAP2.1	*		*				*	*	
BAP2.2		*		*	*	*			*
BAP3.1	*		*		*	*			*
BAP3.2		*		*			*	*	
BAP4.1	*		*		*		*		*
BAP4.2		*		*		*		*	

As matter of fact many combinations of the interoperable profiles can be formed however since there performance concerns and adaptability to the use case leads to choose an optimal one which is UDP, MQTT, NATS, Web Socket. The choice because the UDP from RTDS is faster than the TCP since the use case is innovative frequency service it has to fast enough the VILLAS node works seemly with the MQTT and configuration is plain and simple. The LPC works MQTT and NATS since it's translating the payload from the Jjson message in MQTT to IEEE 2030.5 message structure, NATS will forward the IEEE 2030.5 messages to EMS via Web Socket the web sockets chosen because the NATS is publishing data continuously and there is a need to monitor the status of the frequency constantly by selecting the web sockets.

3.2 Adopted Test bench with LPC in HESS Tec Laboratory

The HESS Tech Laboratory (HESStec) in Valencia serves as one of the testing environments in the InterSTORE project to validate interoperability concepts and software tool at the laboratory level. The test bench implemented in HESSTech focuses on demonstrating the interoperability between Hybrid Energy Storage Systems (HESS), Energy Management Systems (EMS), and the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) developed within WP2, using the IEEE 2030.5 over NATS communication framework.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

3.2.1 Objective of the Test Bench

The purpose of the adopted test bench is to validate the integration of the LPC within the HESStec laboratory setup, acting as the bridge between the local hybrid storage system and the HyDEMS control platform. The bench aims to demonstrate real-time data exchange, hybridization through advanced energy management system, and interoperability under operational use cases providing high power fast services such as Fast Frequency Regulation (FFR), Virtual Inertia Emulation, and Peak Shaving.

3.2.2 Description of the Test Bench

The HESStec test bench is composed of a hybrid energy storage system combining:

- A lithium-ion battery subsystem rated at 250 kW / 250 kWh,
- A supercapacitor subsystem rated at 300 kW / 60 s,
- A bidirectional grid-forming converter capable of operating in both grid-forming and grid-following modes, and
- A local EMS (HyDEMS) installed on a control server connected via Ethernet LAN.

3.2.3 Identification of Interoperability Profiles

The Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) is deployed on a dedicated local server within the same LAN as the EMS and storage devices. Its role is to translate device-level messages, originally in Modbus TCP or MQTT, into standardized IEEE 2030.5-compliant messages exchanged via the NATS messaging protocol.

The communication loop follows these main data flows:

1. Device-to-EMS communication: Real-time data from the converter (voltage, current, power, SoC, SoH) is collected via Modbus and converted by the LPC to IEEE 2030.5 messages (DERStatus, MirrorMetering).
2. EMS-to-Device communication: Control setpoints (active/reactive power commands, mode switching, islanding events) generated by HyDEMS are translated by the LPC into Modbus or MQTT instructions understood by the converter and hybrid controller.

The local NATS broker handles message routing between the LPC and the EMS, ensuring sub-200 ms latency for real-time response applications.

Based on the previous information, several possible interoperable paths were identified:

1. Direct EMS-device communication through Modbus (baseline, non-interoperable).
2. LPC integrated at device level converting Modbus to IEEE 2030.5 directly.
3. LPC deployed on a local server using NATS as intermediary for device-EMS communication.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

4. Dual LPC architecture linking legacy and EMS systems through a bidirectional NATS exchange.

Among these, the Local Server–Single LPC configuration was identified as the most efficient and reliable interoperable link for the HESStec laboratory setup. This configuration (Option 3.3 in D3.3) ensures that all real-time data exchanges occur locally within the LAN—thus minimizing latency—while maintaining interoperability and scalability through standardized IEEE 2030.5 message structures.

In the use case description, its mentioned about the actors participating in the chain to properly formulate the profiling phase through an analysis of the interactions between the actors needed. The message sequence chart illustrates bellow shows the interactions between UC4 actors. More details can be found on Deliverable D2.1, D3.2 and D3.3.

Figure 7 Message Sequence chart representing the interaction between the UC4 actors

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

Table 4 List of actors with types

<i>Actors</i>		
<i>Actor Name</i>	<i>Actor Type</i>	<i>Actor Description</i>
System Operator	Actor	It's the distribution system operator of the internal grid that will provide the services to apply
GRIDLAB	Site	The Lab where the Devices are installed, and the UC will be performed.
HyDems	System	Hybrid energy management system running over the EMS and the DER2.
DER1-EMS	System	Is the Energy management system to control ultracapacitors and battery.

DER1-BMS	System	Is de battery management system.
DER1-BATTERY	Device	Is the High-energy battery device.
DER1-UCMS	System	Is the ultracapacitors management system.
DER1-UCAPS	Device	Is the High-Power ultracapacitors device.
DER1-ACDC	Device	ACDC converter controlled by EMS.
DER1-DCDC	Device	DCDC converter for UCAPS, controlled by EMS.
DER2-PCS3	Device	Inverter to simulate for event and simulation.
PCS4 - Grid Emulator	Device	Inverter to simulate a grid with high impedance.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

The laboratory tests confirmed that the LPC can maintain deterministic communication latencies (<200 ms) while performing continuous bi-directional data exchange and translation between Modbus, MQTT, and IEEE 2030.5 layers.

The integration successfully validated:

- Compatibility of LPC with industrial-grade hybrid storage control hardware.
- Seamless operation of NATS messaging within low latency closed control loops.
- Standardized data representation according to IEEE 2030.5 DERControl and DER-Status resources.

This test bench serves as the reference laboratory configuration for the Spanish pilot, forming the basis for the extended implementation described later in section 4.2.

3.3 Adopted Test Bench with Testing Tool to Validate IEEE 2030.5 in Enel X Laboratory

There are two working software's from the WP2 that has to be validated one is legacy protocol converter that's pillar for interoperability testing in laboratories, the second software is the testing software to test the IEEE 2030.5 natively. The IEEE 2030.5 protocol [9] is the protocol that used in InterStore project as the interoperability communication protocol for both the legacy systems and natively supported systems. The laboratory in Enel X Rome has a Schneider Inverter named as XW pro and an associated gateway called Connex which natively speaks in IEEE 2030.5. One of the important objectives of the InterStore Project is to use IEEE 2030.5 natively in European context, the WP 2.3 developed a testing tool and corresponding testing procedure to test natively supporting IEEE 2030.5.

3.3.1 Description of Test Cases as per Standard

There is standardisation body named as SunSpec Alliance is to define the implementation of IEEE 2030.5 and how to test the protocol supported device in vendor agnostic way. It's very important ant to develop and design a testing procedure vendor agnostic SunSpec qualifies that, for this reason the testing procedures employed in this testing tool as per SunSpec norms [10]. The tests carried out at the Enel X test laboratory in Rome include the test list reported in the SunSpec Common Smart Inverter Profile (CSIP) Conformance Test Procedures: Following the tests implemented in the Testing tool Software developed in T2.3.

The detailed test description is documented in the SunSpec Common Smart Inverter Profile (CSIP) Conformance Test in this deliverable it's summarised as purpose of the test and the test set up.

CORE-001 - HTTP Request

Purpose

Verify server responds correctly for all request types for the configured resource tree.

The HTTP header test verifies required HTTP header and method handling for designated IEEE 2030.5 server resources

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

Setup

- a) Find which functions are supported by the Server and create the resources on the Server.
- b) Make sure the DeviceCapability resource includes the resources created in Step 1.
- c) Record the Client/Server communications.

CORE-002 - HTTP Response

Purpose

Verify server responds correctly to valid and invalid requests. Verify client can follow a resource redirection.

The HTTP response test verifies required HTTP response code and method handling for designated IEEE 2030.5 server resources.

Setup

- a) Find which functions are supported by the Server and create the resources on the Server. There should be at least one resource that supports the 301 Moved Permanently response.
- b) Make sure the DeviceCapability resource includes the resources created in Step 1.

CORE-003 - Polling Interaction

Purpose

Verify client observes polling rates specified in polled resources.

The polling interaction test verifies event polling for DER resources according to CSIP polling requirements. Polling is a mandatory method for getting information from a server, as specified in the IEEE 2030.5 standard. A subscription/notification mechanism is recommended by CSIP to optimize network traffic.

Setup

- a) Verify a DeviceCapability resource exists on the Server, which includes a link to EndDeviceListLink and its subordinate resources.
- b) Pre-register an EndDevice instance for the Client device, including all its required attributes. For example, SFDI, LFDI, and PIN stored in RegistrationLink.
- c) Create a group assignment for the preregistered EndDevice following a multiple layer topology-based grouping as stated in the CSIP guide.
- d) Specify the pollRate for each of the IEEE 2030.5 resources in a way that will determine if the Client is observing the specified poll rate for each resource.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

CORE-004 - List Handling

Purpose

Verify server can handle each of the query parameters associated with list handling.

The list handling test verifies list query and response handling. List and query string search features are an essential part of IEEE 2030.5 list-based resources, which include many DER-related resources.

Setup

a) Create an EndDeviceList with at least three EndDevice instances in the list to exercise the query string parameter searching operation. If the Server cannot meet this condition, create FunctionSetAssignmentsList or DERProgramList with required subordinate resources.

b) Make sure the DeviceCapability resource has the link for EndDeviceList (or FunctionSetAssignmentsList or DERProgramList) for its clients.

CORE-005 - Basic Time

Purpose

The basic time test verifies the discovery and usage of the Time resource provided by a time server and using the Time resource to synchronize with client devices.

Setup

a) Verify a Time resource can be created (or exists) on the Server.

b) Make sure the DeviceCapability resource has the link for Time on the Server.

CORE-006 - Advanced Time

Purpose

Verify time change on server and that the time change is acquired. Verify the time change is logged.

The advanced time test verifies that the Client can obtain the time from the Server and handle advanced scenarios, such as not honoring rolled back clock times.

Setup

a) Verify that a Time resource can be created, or exists, on the Server.

b) Make sure the DeviceCapability resource has the link for Time on the Server.

CORE-007 - Device Capability

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

Purpose

The device capability test verifies that the REF-Client can retrieve the Device Capability (DCAP) resource from an IEEE 2030.5 server and use the resource information provided.

Setup

- a) Verify a DeviceCapability resource exists on the REF-Server and include at least one resource in the DeviceCapability resource.
- b) Record the REF-Client/REF-Server communications.
- c) Configure the network related information about the server so the REF-Client can successfully connect to it.

CORE-008 - Basic End Device

Purpose

The basic end device test verifies the REF-Client can find or POST its EndDevice instance from the IEEE 2030.5 server and can use the resource information, including SFDI, LFDI, FunctionSetAssignmentsListLink, SubscriptionListLink, and LogEventListLink.

Setup

- a) Verify a DeviceCapability resource exists on the REF-Server, which includes a link to EndDeviceListLink and its subordinate resources.
- b) Pre-register an EndDevice instance for the REF-Client device, including all following attributes. For example, SFDI, LFDI, FunctionSetAssignments, Registration/PIN.
- c) Record the REF-Client /REF-Server communications.
- d) Configure the network related information about the server so the REF-Client can successfully connect to it.

CORE-009 - Advanced End Device

Purpose

Verify end device resources are provided and acquired including DERCapability, DERSettings, DERStatus, and DERAvailability. Verify client updates DERCapability, DERSettings, DERStatus, and DERAvailability.

Setup

- a) Verify a DeviceCapability resource exists on the Server, which includes a link to EndDeviceListLink and its subordinate resources.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

b) Pre-register an EndDevice instance for the Client device, including all its required attributes. For example, SFDI/LFDI and PIN which is stored in the RegistrationLink.

CORE-010 - Function Set Assignments

Purpose

The function set assignments test verifies that the Client can get its FunctionSetAssignments from the Server. Each group has an associated DERProgram, and each end device is assigned a DERProgramList with all the DERPrograms, or groups, to which it belongs. The DERProgramList link for each end device is provided using each end device FunctionSetAssignment. This test and all DER event tests configure the end device Client with an EndDevice instance that points to a FunctionSetAssignmentsList for that end device. This FunctionSetAssignmentsList includes a FunctionSetAssignment instance. The FunctionSetAssignment instance includes a DERProgramList link with all the DERPrograms, groups, to which the end device belongs.

Set Up

a) Verify a DeviceCapability resource exists on the Server, which includes a link to EndDeviceListLink and its subordinate resources.

b) Create an EndDeviceList with three EndDevice instances, with one EndDevice instance representing the Client. Make sure the changedTime of the EndDevice instances have a more recent time than the Client instance. This ensures the Client instance is the last in the list.

c) For each EndDevice, these fields must be populated:

- SFDI
- LFDI
- RegistrationLink
- FunctionSetAssignmentsListLink

Short form device identifier. One of the three EndDevice instances must have an SFDI that matches the SFDI of the EUT.

Long form device identifier. One of the three EndDevice instances must have an SFDI that matches the LFDI of the EUT.

Link to the Registration resource of the EndDevice instance under test with the Registration: PIN resource set to 111115.

Link to the FunctionSetAssignmentsList resource of the EndDevice instance.

d) Construct the groups, such as DERPrograms, with the associated primacy values

e) Construct the DERProgramList for the Client.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

- f) Construct a FunctionSetAssignments resource for the Client, which has the DERProgram-ListLink and TimeLink.
- g) Construct a FunctionSetAssignmentsList with the FunctionSetAssignments instance.
- f) For the Client EndDevice instance, assign the FunctionSetAssignmentsListLink to the FunctionSetAssignmentsList.

CORE-011 - Advanced Function Set Assignments

Purpose

Verify provisioning and acquisition of end device with a fifteen-level resource hierarchy. The advanced function set assignments test verifies that the Client can get its FunctionSetAssignments from the Server. CSIP requires the Client to support up to a fifteen deep hierarchy so the Client must be able to support fifteen FSAs.

Setup

a) Create an EndDeviceList with three EndDevice instances, with one EndDevice instance representing the Client. Make sure the changedTime of the EndDevice instances have a more recent time than the Client instance. This ensures the Client instance is the last in the list.

b) For each EndDevice, these fields must be populated:

- LFDI

Long form device identifier. One of the three EndDevice instances must have an SFDI that matches the SFDI of the Client.

- SFDI

Short form device identifier. One of the three EndDevice instances must have an SFDI that matches the LFDI of the Client.

- RegistrationLink

Link to the Registration resource of the EndDevice instance under test with the Registration: PIN resource set to 111115.

- FunctionSetAssignmentsListLink

Link to the FunctionSetAssignmentsList resource of the EndDevice instance.

c) Construct a FunctionSetAssignmentsList resource for the Client with fifteen FunctionSetAssignments following the CSIP topology/non-topology recommendations.

4 Configuration of Interoperability Profiles

This chapter aims to explain in detail about the configuration of the interoperable profiles which is chosen in 3.1, 3.2 and 3.3. In each use cases the configurations will vary depends upon the use case the technologies it uses. This chapter divided into 3 parts the 4.1 details the configurations used with LPC in the RWTH laboratory and 4.2 the configurations used HESS Tech laboratory followed by testing tool how to set up it for the tests. The need of the configurations arises from fact that what to operate for a specific set of operations not all operations are covered in one single configuration file. Different configurations provide different operating modes, consider a generic protocol converter where it uses many protocols as its output from a real hardware or simulator, it come down to the choice of interoperable profile chosen in chapter 3 to configure the protocol converter or other actors in chain according to the interoperability profile. By applying the configuration introduce less redundancy and less prone to errors or bugs. The Introduction of configuration gives a room for experimenting with different possible scenarios for example the data rate of transmission from the simulator and the time precisions clocked in nanoseconds. As a result of tuning the configuration provides a range of outcomes depends on the metric of concern one can pick the best outcome results that achieves desired use case results.

4.1 Adopted Configuration for Basic Application Interoperability Profile with LPC in RWTH Laboratory

Configurations applied on the interoperability interfaces between different actors in the interoperability chain. It's identified that there are several interfaces present for configurations. Starting from RTDS <-> VILLAS, VILLAS<->LPC, LPC<->EMS. The formulation of configuration based several aspects the communication technique for instance MQTT, Web Socket, rate of speed of transmission, the payload structure Json, xml.

4.1.1 Configuration of RTDS to VILLAS NODE

Before initiating the simulation in the RTDS, configurations must be established to define the input and output connections to the simulator. These configurations specify how data flows into and out of the RTDS, this configuration is partially the part in the RTDS, and other half is in VILLAS. The part of the RTDS is connected to its network interface called card depicted in figure 2. The process of the configuration from the RTDS simulator is explained as follows. First and foremost is the Hardware level Configuration in the RS CAD, to carry out this the model created in the in the draft case in the RSCAD Draft (Hardware Mode), during the compilation, the RSCAD generates the .cfg and .out files that define what hardware modules such as GTNET, GTFPGA, GTSYNC etc is need for the model. Without compilation, Runtime has no knowledge which cards the model that developed is needed in our case it's GTNET Card is identified after the compilation. Next step is to configure the GT NET Card under the option Configuration ->Rack Configuration this comes with the selection of the Rack where the GTNET Card and the slot where the GTNET card is installed, configuration window appears to assign the firmware in our case is GTNET_SKT and assign port A or B, the port A stands for network port such as eth0 and assigned IP address to each interface. The above can be named as Rack Configuration things need to run the simulation in the RTDS. The next level configuration is the simulation Model configuration how the simulation model communicates through that hardware.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

Figure 8 GTNET-SKT block to set up the outgoing configuration

The figure6 depicts the outgoing communication from the RTDS to the remote device, the IP is the Ip of the remote device followed by its port , as it's evident that there are local and remote port , the local port for the GTNET card that uses inside the RTDS and Remote port is as that of the device of interest to connect to receive the signal from the RTDS. The mode of communication can be UDP or TCP. The receiving end is the VILLAS the protocol converter that convert from UDP to MQTT.

```

ontfig.conf
stats = 1.0

nodes = {
  acs-rtids = [
    type = "socket"
    format = "gtnet"

    in = {
      address = "*:12000"
      signals = (
        { name = "timestamp", type = "float", enabled = true },
        { name = "frequency", type = "float", enabled = true }
      )
    }

    out = {
      address = "134.130.169.107:12000"
    }
  ]
}

mqtt = {
  type = "mqtt"
  format = "json"
  host = "mqtt_der"
  in = {
    format = "json"
    subscribe = "/rtids-mqtt",
    signals = (
      { name = "villasIslandingMode", type = "float", enabled = true },
      { name = "villasLP4Shed", type = "float", enabled = true }
    )
  }
  out = {
    publish = "/mqtt-rtids",
    format = "json",
    flatten = true
  }
}
}

```

Figure 9 VILLAS NODE Configuration

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

The nodes stand for villas node each node in villas represent a protocol converter you have many protocol converters spawned simultaneously. The configuration in villas is structured as JSON, where the acs-rtids represent the incoming connection from the RTDS type of communication is socket (opted UDP as depicted in figure 6) and format is GTNET (the hardware card) in address refers to the RTDS local port and wildcard subscription means that any IP address that runs on port 12000, out stands for the device where the message has to send with its IP Address and port, signal mapping linking those simulations variables to communication data fields in the GTNET block refers to the values that comes from RTDS. The next part is the outgoing protocol from VILLAS node which is MQTT since the communication bidirectional there is needs to mention the “in” and “out” of the MQTT. The “in” state refers that the messages will be subscribed “/rtids-mqtt” on this topic this will send the messages to the RTDS as it’s evident that there are signals named villasIslandingMode VillasLP4Shed are the control commands activated received from EMS to act in the banshee microgrid in the RTDS. The “out” refers that the message that goes from VILLAS to other actor in the chain and it’s published under the topic “/mqtt-rtids”.

4.1.2 Configuration of To and from of LPC

LPC (legacy protocol converter) [11] can be considered as the roundabout is apart of the traffic system in roads. In our contest what comes is that protocol from the VILLAS which is MQTT and the same shall be send back to the VILLAS in the bidirectional communication. The legacy protocol converter is developed for converting legacy protocols into IEEE 2030.5 for this to happen there is need to configure the LPC to make this protocol translator. The configuration added below

Figure 10 Configuration of LPC

```
connections:
- name: NATS-Server
type: NATS
host: host.docker.internal
port: 4222
reconnect: true
- name: MQTT-HESS
type: MQTT
host: mqtt_der
port: 1883
- name: ModbusTCP-battery1
type: Modbus
host: host.docker.internal
```

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

port: 5020

transformations:

- name: MQTT Client publishes status from RTDS

description: LPC converts MQTT message (in JSON form) containing DERStatus to NATS (in JSON form)

validate-ieee2030-5: true

connections:

incoming-connection:

- MQTT-HESS

incoming-topic: /mqtt-rtds

incoming-format: JSON

outgoing-connection:

- NATS-Server

outgoing-topic: der/status/to-nats

outgoing-format: XML

to-outgoing:

to-topic: der/status/to-nats

message: |-

```
<mirrorMeterReadingList>
```

```
<mirrorMeterReading>
```

```
<description>Grid Frequency</description>
```

```
<lastUpdateTime>$timestamp</lastUpdateTime>
```

```
<reading>
```

```
<value>
```

```
<lpc:mapping>
```

```
<path type="float32">/0/data/0</path>
```

```
</lpc:mapping>
```

```
</value>
```

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

```
</reading>
<readingType>
<phase><value>64</value></phase>
<powerOfTenMultiplier><value>0</value></powerOfTenMultiplier>
<uom><value>33</value></uom>
</readingType>
<mrid><value>1</value></mrid>
</mirrorMeterReading>
<mirrorMeterReading>
<description>Measurement Timestamp Seconds</description>
<lastUpdateTime>${timestamp}</lastUpdateTime>
<reading>
<value>
<lpc:mapping>
<path type="int64">/0/ts/origin/0</path>
</lpc:mapping>
</value>
</reading>
<readingType>
<phase><value>64</value></phase>
<powerOfTenMultiplier><value>0</value></powerOfTenMultiplier>
<uom><value>0</value></uom>
</readingType>
<mrid><value>2</value></mrid>
</mirrorMeterReading>
<mirrorMeterReading>
<description>Measurement Timestamp Nanoseconds</description>
```

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

```
<lastUpdateTime>$timestamp</lastUpdateTime>
<reading>
<value>
<lpc:mapping>
<path type="int64">/0/ts/origin/1</path>
</lpc:mapping>
</value>
</reading>
<readingType>
<phase><value>64</value></phase>
<powerOfTenMultiplier><value>0</value></powerOfTenMultiplier>
<uom><value>0</value></uom>
</readingType>
<mrid><value>3</value></mrid>
</mirrorMeterReading>
<all>3</all>
<results>3</results>
</mirrorMeterReadingList>
```

- name: NATS Client publishes status to RTDS

description: LPC converts NATS message (in JSON form) containing DERStatus to RTDS via MQTT (in JSON form)

validate-ieee2030-5: true

connections:

incoming-connection:

- NATS-Server

incoming-topic: der/status/from-nats

incoming-format: XML

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

outgoing-connection:

- MQTT-HESS

outgoing-topic: /rtds-mqtt

outgoing-format: JSON

to-outgoing:

to-topic: /rtds-mqtt

message: |-

```
[[{"ts": {"origin": [timestamp, 0]}, "sequence": {"lpc:mapping": {"path": "DERStatus/sequence", "type": "int32"}}, {"data": [{"lpc:mapping": {"path": "DERStatus/villasIslandingMode", "type": "float32"}}, {"lpc:mapping": {"path": "DERStatus/villasLP4Shed", "type": "float32"}}]]]
```

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

The configuration follows the yaml data structure and the connections starts with NATS - Server where the nats clients connecting for publish and subscribe the server runs on the port 4222, the LPC currently accepts two protocols Modbus and MQTT and it connects in corresponding ports. The section transformation in yaml configuration is where describes the incoming connection under the key "name": MQTT Client publishes status from RTDS this is the data comes from the RTDS via VILLAS the incoming protocol is MQTT important is to remember the incoming topic this should be the same as that mentioned in the VILLAS configuration in figure 10 and data format is JSON, the outgoing-connection is in NATS-Server where the nats clients connects the outgoing topic "der/status/to-nats" format in XML from incoming format which is JSON this exactly where the conversion to IEEE 2030.5 happens which natively supports XML as data format. The message section is where the message has to be converted into IEEE 2003.5 from incoming formats wrapped up in JSON, since the incoming messages are frequency and time the parameters for monitoring maps into the mirror metering resource in the IEEE 2030.5. Inside the <value> </value> represents the lpc mapping the path type contains the data from the source to transform in this case the JSON send via MQTT. Apparently, this message is published to the der/stats/to-nats by a nats client connected to the NATS server

The Second transformation is part of the duplex communication the messages coming from the EMS is in the IEEE 2030.5 XML format this will be converted to JSON, as it's evident that the message is coming via incoming-topic names as "der/status/from-nats" is subscribed by NATS client and published the converted message via MQTT under the outgoing-topic: /rtds-mqtt

4.1.3 Configuration of EMS to LPC

The EMS is another actor in the Interoperability chain since the EMS is running on web browser the browser only supports http-based connection not directly the publish subscribe mechanism for this reason there is need of another protocol that supports the browser which is in this case is WebSocket. The reason behind the WebSocket is that it will take the real time streaming values in the use case the frequency is publishing continuously by NATS and the websocket does accept this values and display it in the server. The configuration between the web socket and NATS depicted configured through the below code

Figure 11 Configuration of EMS to LPC

```
async def main():
try:
header1 = ["frequency"]
header2 = ["timestamp"]
with open('/app/data/gridfrequency.csv', 'w') as f:
f.write(','.join(header1) + ',' + ','.join(header2) + '\n')
print("CSV file cleared on startup")
except Exception as e:
```

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

```
print(f"Could not clear CSV file: {e}")

print("[DEBUG] About to connect to NATS")

global nc

nc = NATS()

for _ in range(10):

    try:

        await nc.connect(servers=["nats://nats_server:4222"])

        print("Connected to NATS")

        break

    except ErrNoServers:

        await asyncio.sleep(2)

    else:

        print("Could not connect to NATS. Exiting.")

return

await nc.subscribe("der/status/to-nats", cb=message_handler_from_nats)

print("[DEBUG] About to start WebSocket server")

await websockets.serve(websocket_handler, "0.0.0.0", 8765)

print("WebSocket server listening on :8765")

try:

    await asyncio.Future()

except KeyboardInterrupt:

    print("Shutting down...")
```

The code depicts that it tries to connect to the NATS Server first when it starts from the docker compose where all the micro services connected via docker network. Once it gets connected

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

to the server then it will tries to subscribe the message on the subject which is ("der/status/to-nats", the message will be handled by the message handler from mats this function is does the message transfer to the grid operations those functions not listed above and the processed message send via WebSocket to the browser. The other way communication is that WebSocket handler will receive the command from the EMS this message form the corresponding xml and send it via NATS topic "der/status/from-nats". The complete docker compose version below.

Figure 12 Docker Compose with all services listed

```
version: '2.7'

services:

node_rwth:

container_name: villas_rwth_interscada

image: registry.git.rwth-aachen.de/acs/public/villas/node

ports:

- "12000:12000/udp"

volumes:

- ./config.conf:/etc/node/config.conf

- ./data:/workspaces/node/data/

command:

- node

- -d

- info

- /etc/node/config.conf

restart: always

networks:

- single_lpc_network

nats_server:

image: nats:latest
```

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

```
container_name: nats_server

ports:
- "4222:4222"

networks:
- single_lpc_network

lpc_der:
image: interstore/legacy-protocol-converter:latest

extra_hosts:
- "host.docker.internal:host-gateway"

container_name: lpc_der

environment:
- TZ=Europe/Berlin
- JAVA_TOOL_OPTIONS=--add-opens=java.base/java.net=ALL-UNNAMED

volumes:
- ./conf/lpc_der_config.yaml:/app/conf/config_lpc_der.yml
- ./conf/log4j2.xml:/app/log-config/log4j2.xml
- ./logs/lpc_der:/app/logs

restart: "always"

depends_on:
- nats_server

networks:
- single_lpc_network

nats-endpoint:

hostname: nats-ep

build: ./nats_endpoint
```

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

container_name: nats_agent

depends_on:

- nats_server

environment:

- PYTHONUNBUFFERED=1

- TZ=Europe/Berlin

ports:

- "8765:8765"

volumes:

- ./data:/app/data/

- /var/run/docker.sock:/var/run/docker.sock

networks:

- single_lpc_network

react_gui:

build: ./Tauri_React_GUI

container_name: front_end

ports:

- "3000:3000"

depends_on:

- nats_server

networks:

- single_lpc_network

networks:

single_lpc_network:driver: bridge

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

Docker Compose configuration orchestrates a distributed real-time grid monitoring system by deploying five interconnected microservices that communicate over a shared Docker bridge network named `single_lpc_network`. At the foundation of the architecture is the NATS server, which serves as the central message broker running on port 4222, facilitating publish-subscribe communication between backend services without requiring direct point-to-point connections. The Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) service acts as the protocol translation layer between the RTDS real-time digital simulator and the NATS messaging infrastructure, consuming grid frequency measurements from the simulator via the VILLASnode service and publishing them as XML-formatted messages to NATS topics while simultaneously subscribing to control commands that need to be forwarded back to the RTDS system. VILLASnode provides the low-latency UDP-based communication interface on port 12000, bridging the gap between the RTDS hardware simulator and the containerized software ecosystem by handling the real-time data acquisition and transmission requirements. The NATS endpoint service, implemented as a Python-based WebSocket server listening on port 8765, functions as the critical bridge between the backend NATS messaging system and the frontend user interface by maintaining bidirectional connections—subscribing to grid frequency data from NATS and broadcasting it to connected WebSocket clients while simultaneously receiving user commands from the frontend and publishing them back to NATS for eventual delivery to the RTDS simulator. Finally, the React GUI service provides the web-based frontend interface accessible on port 3000, connecting to the NATS endpoint's WebSocket server to visualize real-time grid frequency measurements, display load shedding events with calculated latencies, and allow operators to issue islanding mode commands. All services are deployed within the same Docker bridge network, enabling automatic DNS-based service discovery where containers can reference each other by service name rather than IP address, creating a loosely coupled yet highly coordinated system where the failure or restart of any individual service does not require reconfiguration of dependent services. The architecture notably eliminates the previously used MQTT broker and NATS-to-MQTT bridge services, streamlining the message flow by having the NATS endpoint communicate directly with the NATS server, reducing latency and architectural complexity while maintaining the same functional capabilities for real-time grid monitoring and control operations.

4.2 Adopted Configuration for Basic Application Interoperability Profile with LPC in HESS Tech Laboratory

This section presents the adopted BAIOP configuration used in the HESStec GridLab platform in Spain. Building upon the laboratory validation described in section 3.2, this configuration demonstrates how the interoperability framework defined in WP2 and WP3 was applied at the platform level, enabling interaction between hybrid energy assets, EMS, and upper-layer control systems.

4.2.1 Overview of Configuration

The adopted configuration corresponds to the “Local Server – Single LPC” deployment strategy (Option 3.3 from D3.3), where the LPC and a local NATS broker are hosted on a local industrial PC within the HESStec lab network. This ensures that the local control loop (devices–LPC–EMS) remains fully operational and deterministic, even in the absence of cloud connectivity, while maintaining optional synchronization with remote systems via a secondary cloud-based NATS server.

The configuration supports the following objectives:

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

- Enable real-time bi-directional communication between the hybrid storage converter and the HyDEMS EMS via LPC.
- Validate interoperability under IEEE 2030.5 data models using NATS as a communication backbone.
- Verify compliance with the Basic Application Interoperability Profile (BAIOP) designed for hybrid energy management.

4.2.2 Communication Architecture and Mapping

The communication architecture is organized into three logical layers:

1. Device Layer:

- Grid-forming converter, battery management system (BMS), and ultracapacitor controller communicate over Modbus TCP.
- Key data include instantaneous active/reactive power, frequency, voltage, and state variables (SoC, SoF).

2. Interoperability Layer (LPC):

- The LPC receives Modbus data and translates them into IEEE 2030.5 DER resources.
- Outgoing commands from the EMS are mapped back to Modbus or MQTT control registers.
- Configuration and mapping rules are defined in YAML-based schemas following the BAP→BAIOP transformation principles.
- Example mappings:
 - *DERStatus.PowerActive* ↔ *Modbus Register 40001*
 - *DERControl.ReactivePowerSetpoint* ↔ *Modbus Register 40105*
 - *DERStatus.SoC* ↔ *Modbus Register 40210*

3. EMS/Platform Layer:

- The HyDEMS EMS subscribes to the local NATS topics (*/hesstec/der/status* and */hesstec/der/control*) for device telemetry and control:
 - /hesstec/der/status* – for device measurements and system state,
 - /hesstec/der/control* – for EMS-issued setpoints and operating commands.
- Visualization dashboards display real-time power, frequency, and SoC data, while control algorithms compute response actions under FFR and virtual inertia scenarios. The EMS publishes control messages that are then translated by the LPC and executed by the converter and battery controllers.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

- Data are visualized in real time, while control algorithms execute frequency or voltage support commands, transmitted back via NATS and converted by LPC.

The BAIOP testing within the GridLab environment followed the structured methodology described in Section 2, covering:

- Functional interoperability – ensuring that data exchange supports continuous and correct control actions.
- Performance interoperability – validating that message latency and throughput meet the operational requirements of hybrid frequency and inertia services.
- Semantic interoperability – verifying alignment between Modbus parameters and IEEE 2030.5 data models.

The following results were observed:

- Average round-trip communication latency: 150–180 ms for fast dynamic grid services.
- Stable synchronization between converter, BMS, and EMS signals.
- Correct execution of DERControl messages and telemetry mirroring in IEEE 2030.5 format. IT also demonstrated successful message routing between local and cloud NATS instances, proving resilience and scalability for larger deployments.

4.3 Adopted Configuration with Testing Tool to Validate IEEE 2030.5 in Enel X Laboratory

The purpose of the testing tool to validate the conformance test, the architecture of the testing tool is detailed in the task 2.4. The testing tool consists of a backend and frontend, the backend of the software is a server based on the REST api architecture because the IEEE 2030.5 protocol is REST api based protocol, for this reason for web services the chosen coding language is Java and Spring boot as the framework. The front end written in React framework. There are two other important services for seamless communication from the client to server those are an ad hoc server based on the C++ and NATS. The adhoc server is the software component makes the socket communication with proper encryption and certificate authority (CA) issued certificates. The NATS is considered as extra wrapper on ad hoc server to send the request to the backend of the software. There are many possible architectures one of the possible ones is to host all the components of the testing tool on premise where the testing device is present the advantage of this is that quick and easy set up for rapid tests however this doesn't leverage the functionality of the NATS based geographical distributed testing. The entitled envision is that to use the NATS is to tests assess from a geographically agnostic locations, this gives platform to able to gather data from different location that can be improved for testing the automate the testing procedures while rolling out the changes to one. To achieve this there is a need to host the java spring-based server in the cloud premises where the IEEE 2030.5 resources are saved for conformance testing. The other piece is the connectivity software that will hosted in on premises where the tests conducting, by this way the direct communication with device will be solid and fast more reliability in connection. This style of testing architecture brings to adapt to both aggregator as the communication agent to the DER and DER it's self can communicate independently. Not only this but also by

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

hosting the IEEE 2030.5 server which is the part of the testing tool in the cloud can leverage testing simultaneously to many DER's imagine a situation that the entire IEEE 2030.5 system of DER devices increased exponentially this does prove the scalability of the proposed testing tool.

4.3.1 Device Configuration

First and foremost is that device configuration is necessary before the test once the device configuration is known to the testing software then there is no need to repeat it again. The configuration of the device in our case it's an XW pro a Schinder Inverter it comes with a GUI as shown in figure 13. In the GUI [12] there is an IEEE 2030.5 toggle button this has to be enabled its slider sliding right will make it enabled to use IEEE 2030.5. There are two modes to operate the remote control and the local control, the remote control does the communication with the remote software usually the utility software that's deployed in some servers remotely in our case the testing tool which is hosted remotely in computer that runs on ubuntu it can be hosted in windows and mac too because the test software use docker compose this will make operating systems agnostic. Next is that the Ip address of the gateway where the XW pro inverter connected, the inverter is managed by a gateway provided by Schnider electric and port is 8443 or 443 for https communication. The server long form identifier is the certificate fingerprint in earlier its mentioned about the CA certificates, how it works in the IEEE 2030.5 context is that a device has a certificate with public signed by a Root CA this certificate file usually in .pem known as privacy enhanced mail format or. pkcs (public key cryptography standards). The testing tool has a certificate signed by root CA this certificate has a public key, there is a parameter named SLFDI (Server Long Form Device Identifier) which is result of performing a SHA256 operation over the certificate in the testing tool. The generated SLFDI has to be entered in the form which selected in the form. The server DCAP path is where the device first has to entered according to the protocol. There are couple other identifiers they are SFDI and LFDI this time it's of the client, which is the XW pro device, the formulation of SFDI is stated as per the IEEE 2030.5 documentation, The SFDI SHALL be the certificate fingerprint left-truncated to 36 bits. For display purposes, this SHALL be expressed as 11 decimal (base 10) digits, with an additional sum-of-digits checksum digit right concatenated and the LFDI. The LFDI SHALL be the certificate fingerprint left-truncated to 160 bits (20 octets). For display purposes, this SHALL be expressed as 40 hexadecimal (base 16) digits in groups of four. The server poll interval is how often poll to the server from the device and the server. The server pin is the identification pin that the server has to possess for successful communication in this case the testing tool which have a server to store these values. This is got tested in the registration conformance testing by default the pin is 111115. Click apply button to make the changes effective and once the client communicates with the testing tool if it makes the successful handshake the connection status will be green else it will be red.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

Figure 13 GUI of the IEEE 2030.5 device

4.3.2 Testing tool configuration

Figure 14 Docker compose of the testing tool

```

version: '3.8'

services:
  ieee2030-server:
    build:
    context: .
    dockerfile: adhoc/Dockerfile
    container_name: ieee2030-server
    ports:

```

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

```
- "443:443"
volumes:
- ./adhoc:/app/certs:ro
restart: unless-stopped
networks:
- back-nats
java-backend:
build:
context: ./interstore
dockerfile: Dockerfile
image: nithinmanuel9/interstoretestieeee2030-server:3.1
container_name: java-backend
depends_on:
- nats
environment:
- NATS_URL=nats://nats-server:4222
- SERVER_PORT=8080
- SERVER_ADDRESS=0.0.0.0
- JAVA_OPTS=-Xms512m -Xmx1024m -Djava.net.preferIPv4Stack=true -Djava.net.preferIPv4Addresses=true
ports:
- "8080:8080"
volumes:
- ./interstore/app/certs:/app/certs:ro
networks:
- back-nats
restart: unless-stopped
```

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

react-browser:

build:

context: ./react-browser

dockerfile: Dockerfile

hostname: react-browser

container_name: react-browser

depends_on:

- java-backend

ports:

- "3000:3000"

volumes:

- ./react-browser:/react

- /react/node_modules

command: ["npm","start"]

networks:

- back-nats

restart: unless-stopped

nats:

image: nats:latest

container_name: nats-server

hostname: nats-server

ports:

- "4222:4222"

- "8222:8222"

command: ["--jetstream", "--addr", "0.0.0.0", "--port", "4222", "-m", "8222"]

networks:

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

- back-nats

restart: unless-stopped

networks: back-nats

The user interacts with the GUI provided by the react-browser service, which serves a React-based web interface accessible on port 3000. The react-browser service communicates directly with the java-backend service, which implements the IEEE 2030.5 REST API server running on port 8080. Both the react-browser and java-backend services are connected through the back-nats Docker network, enabling direct HTTP communication between the frontend and backend. The java-backend service depends on the NATS messaging server (running on nats://nats-server:4222) for asynchronous message-based communication and event streaming, with NATS configured in JetStream mode for persistent messaging capabilities. Additionally, there's an iee2030-server service that runs separately on HTTPS port 443, providing secure access to the IEEE 2030.5 protocol implementation. The NATS server exposes two ports: 4222 for client connections from the java-backend, and 8222 for monitoring and management purposes. All four services (react-browser, java-backend, iee2030-server, and nats) are connected through a single back-nats network, creating a simplified architecture where the frontend directly communicates with the backend services without an intermediate middleware layer. The java-backend is configured with specific JVM parameters (-Xms512m -Xmx1024m) and IPv4 stack preferences to optimize performance, while all services are set to restart automatically unless explicitly stopped, ensuring high availability in the production environment.

5 Test Results

The test results chapter contains the outcome of different laboratories in 3 different locations based on three different uses cases. The outcomes of these tests prove that the software tools developed in the WP2 such as LPC and testing tool served its purpose as per expected.

5.1 Test Results Basic Application Interoperability Profile with LPC in RWTH Laboratory

In the design of experiments the test is well described, and the end goal of this test is that innovative frequency service such as load shedding, the restoration of the service happens in the allowable time range in which is in milliseconds. Most interesting aspect is that the latency of the system how fast the system will recover in the given experiment set up. The banshee microgrid in the RTDS runs on 50Hz frequency connected and communicated via Interoperable testing methodology chosen in chapter 3. In figure 4 Shows the GUI of the EMS system whereby a button click will trigger the virtual Islanding condition, once the Islanding mode is activated there is a sharp drop in the frequency marked as virtual islanding in the figure 15. The drop is frequency cause the grid in unstable mode in this situation there is need to restore the stability of the grid by applying the load shedding. The load shedding function activated by the Interoperability chain this is not the feature of the EMS however part of the interoperability logical handling based on the value of the frequency. This approach makes semantic interoperability downs to the payload structure of the IEEE 2030.5. As result of the load shedding action triggered by the interoperable chain the load in the RTDS banshee microgrid will be shed bring back the frequency in the desirable level to operate the grid. The critical aspect of this entire operation is how fast the system recovers from the instability which is measured as the round-trip time from the time which the manually trigger the islanding from the GUI to the point where the frequency brings back to normal these values are depicted in yellow in the table 5. Most appreciated and foreseen outcomes are that excellent functioning of the Interoperability experimental scenario orchestrated by IEEE 2030.5 protocol and the frequency restoration achieved within allowable range i.e. normally 500ms, tested multiple time and recorded the same outcome.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

Grid Recovery Time: 333 ms (Latency)

Figure 15 Use Case 4 Innovative frequency service (Load Shedding)

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

Table 5 frequency vs time recorded latency

Entry	Time	Frequency (Hz)	Latency (ms)
1	10:30:45.318	50.0000	-
2	10:30:45.652	50.0000	-
3	10:30:45.985	50.0000	-
4	10:30:46.319	50.0000	-
5	10:30:46.652	50.0000	-
6	10:30:46.986	50.0000	-
7	10:30:47.319	50.0000	-
8	10:30:47.653	50.0000	-
9	10:30:47.986	49.8259	-
10	10:30:48.319	49.7550	-
11	10:30:48.653	49.8014	333
12	10:30:48.653	49.8066	-
13	10:30:49.986	49.8057	-
14	10:30:49.320	49.8058	-
15	10:30:49.653	49.8062	-
16	10:30:50.987	49.8055	-
17	10:30:50.320	49.8059	-
18	10:30:50.654	49.8062	-
19	10:30:51.987	49.8054	-
20	10:30:51.321	49.8061	-

5.2 Test Result of LPC in HESS Tech Laboratory

This section presents the laboratory validation results of the Legacy Protocol Converter (LPC) deployed in the HESStec laboratory testing environment. The objective is to evaluate the performance of the interoperability software tools in real-time operation during a grid frequency disturbance event with use case number 4 (UC4 shown in Figure 16) and to demonstrate their capability to support hybrid energy storage systems delivering fast frequency services. The tests were carried out on a grid-forming converter integrated with a hybrid storage unit composed of an ultracapacitor (UCAP) module and a lithium-ion battery system. The experiment replicates a representative frequency event, enabling assessment of response time, coordination of hybrid assets, and compliance with the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) defined for Use Case 4.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

Figure 16 Testing Scenario for T3.4– VI (UC4–Innovative Frequency services BESS)

5.2.1 Virtual Inertia Response to a Frequency Event

For this test of UC4 in laboratory environment, a frequency disturbance was created. The grid-forming converter, equipped with virtual inertia emulation functionality, was controlled through the LPC–NATS interoperability chain. As explained in previous deliverable D3.2 and D3.3, the LPC translated Modbus-based device measurements and control commands into IEEE 2030.5-compliant messages and ensured real-time exchange with the EMS.

The results of this test are shown in Figures 17 to 18. Obtained results show that the hybrid storage system responded immediately after the frequency deviation was detected. The UCAP subsystem delivered the initial high-power, high-frequency component of the response, stabilizing the frequency nadir within the first few hundred milliseconds. Shortly after, the battery subsystem ramped up smoothly to provide sustained energy support, maintaining frequency restoration with lower-frequency power injection. This demonstrates the correct hybridization behavior expected for fast frequency support.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

Figure 17 Laboratory experimental results of VI service: Frequency at the POC with full time window

Figure 18 Laboratory experimental results of VI service: Frequency at the POC with zoom at the first frequency event

The measured frequency trace and storage power outputs confirm that the LPC-enabled communication path introduces no significant delay or distortion to the control loop. The converter followed the virtual inertia control profile accurately, validating the suitability of the LPC architecture for real-time grid-support functions.

Figure 19 illustrate the captured dynamic power output of both storage elements during the event. The UCAP reached its peak output almost instantaneously, providing the fast inertial contribution. The battery then delivered a slower, energy-rich response, ensuring overall stability and preventing rebound effects. This coordination was achieved under the EMS logic with all communication routed through the LPC.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

Figure 19 Laboratory experimental results of VI service: Output power of storage elements

The smooth transition between UCAP and battery output confirms the acceptable fast response of the deployed software tools as well as the corrected action of the developed hybrid control algorithms which receive the required measurements and setpoints with minimal latency. Throughout the test, the continuity of IEEE 2030.5 messaging via LPC was validated, with no data losses or communication freezes observed.

5.2.2 KPI Evaluation for UC4

The performance was assessed using some of the selected KPIs defined for Use Case 4 (Fast Power Service). Table 6 summaries the calculated KPIs for the test scenario.

Table 6: KPI analysis for VI test-UC4

KPI	Description	Event	CAN based	LPC based	Result
Nadir (Hz)	Minimum frequency during disturbance	49.55	49.7	49.68	Pass
RoCoF (Hz/s)	Rate of Change of Frequency	1.33	0.9	1	Pass
Response Time (ms)	Time from event start to first power injection	N/A	200 ms	180 ms	Pass

Both Nadir and RoCoF remain within the acceptable performance range defined by the project, demonstrating that the LPC-based architecture is fully capable of supporting fast ancillary services at the laboratory scale.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

5.2.4 Comparison: LPC-Based Integration vs. CAN-Based Approach

A comparison between the legacy CAN-based communication and the new LPC-IEEE 2030.5-NATS chain was performed to quantify capabilities in responsiveness and data handling. The LPC implementation showed equivalent control performance and, in several cases, enhanced stability in message timing, thanks to the clearer separation between measurement, translation, and publication layers.

The virtual inertia test revealed no degradation in the response speed compared to the CAN approach. The LPC approach offers far greater interoperability and aligns with the broader goals of InterSTORE for flexible, hybrid and grid-forming systems.

5.2.5 Summary

The laboratory tests confirm that the LPC preserves real-time operational capability during fast frequency response events and supports hybrid storage coordination without adding observable latency. The system achieved full compliance with the UC4 KPIs and demonstrated a smooth and reliable virtual inertia response.

The successful results validate the LPC as a robust and future-proof interoperability solution for hybrid energy storage and grid-forming converter applications, paving the way for real-world deployment and integration into European flexibility markets.

5.3 Test Result of Testing Tool in Enel X Tech Laboratory

The testing tool is deployed in a Linux operating system supported connected to the gateway with RJ45 cable, where the gateway is from Schinder named as Connex. The gateway is connected to XWpro the inverter supports IEEE 2030.5 natively the device under test. The docker compose runs in the Linux machine makes the communication with the software running in the gateway. The initial steps are handshake between the Device and the testing tool to verify that the testing tool has appropriate CA certificates to authorise the further communication. The Device will send http get requests to the test tool requesting for device capability GET /dcap HTTP/1.1 and client will receive the response from server which is logged with GET /dcap with 200 OK as status code, the NATS client will connect to the NATS server and publish this response to the validation part of the test server to validate against the golden standard as shown in the figure 20

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

```

ieee2030-frontend | Server running at http://18.232.7.53:3001
ieee2030-client   | IEEE 2030.5 client test version 0.2.11 -- compiled: Sep 12 2025
ieee2030-client   | load device certificate: ptl_dev.x509
ieee2030-client   |   lfdi: 0671c144d27dc9e612afe7dc6c79ec089ed3dcc5
ieee2030-client   |   sfdi: 17298934539
ieee2030-client   | loaded certificate "./certs/sat-root.pem"
ieee2030-client   | --- conn = 0x647a36e06760 -->
ieee2030-client   | GET /dcap HTTP/1.1
ieee2030-client   | Date: Thu, 20 Nov 2025 00:53:13 GMT
ieee2030-client   | Host: 18.232.7.53:443
ieee2030-client   | Accept: application/sep+xml; level=-51
ieee2030-client   |
ieee2030-client   | <-- conn = 0x647a36e06760 ---
ieee2030-client   | HTTP/1.1 200 OK
ieee2030-client   | Content-Type: application/sep+xml
ieee2030-client   | Content-Length: 262
ieee2030-client   | X-Server-LFDI: faba4524ff2d734befaad8320384c41b049be845
ieee2030-client   | X-Server-SFDI: 673041823510
ieee2030-client   |
ieee2030-client   | GET /dcap: 200
ieee2030-client   | <DeviceCapability xmlns="http://ieee.org/2030.5" href="/dcap">
ieee2030-client   |   <TimeLink href="/dcap/tm"/>
ieee2030-client   |   <EndDeviceListLink all="1" href="/edev"/>
ieee2030-client   | </DeviceCapability>
ieee2030-client   | Attempting to connect to NATS server at 18.232.7.53:4222...
ieee2030-client   | Connected to NATS server successfully
ieee2030-client   | Message published to 'response.client' subject successfully
ieee2030-client   |
ieee2030-client   | net_close
ieee2030-client   | Connection closed

```

Figure 20 Device Capability request from the Client (Device)

The test are conformance tests validating as per SunSpec testing procedures listed in the chapter 3. The tests execute in a concurrent manner the client will ask to multiple resources on the same time this is the one of the fundamental key architectures of the IEEE 2030.5 protocol enabling the device can read the write to multiple resources of the IEEE 2030.5 protocol on simultaneously by fully compactable with the synchronous communication of the REST Api.

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

```

ieee2030-server | [1763599993] Connection from 54.147.91.126:41764
ieee2030-server | SSL handshake successful with 54.147.91.126
ieee2030-server |
ieee2030-server | ===== Incoming HTTP Request =====
ieee2030-server | Client IP: 54.147.91.126
ieee2030-server | Method: GET
ieee2030-server | Path: /dcap
ieee2030-server | Version: HTTP/1.1
ieee2030-server | Headers:
ieee2030-server | Date: Thu, 20 Nov 2025 00:53:13 GMT
ieee2030-server | Host: 18.232.7.53:443
ieee2030-server | Accept: application/sep+xml; level=-51
ieee2030-server | Body: (empty)
ieee2030-server | =====
ieee2030-server | Forwarding to URL: http://java-backend:8080/dcap [Method: GET]
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.630Z INFO 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] o.a.c.c.C.[Tomcat].[localhost].[/]
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.631Z INFO 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] o.s.web.servlet.DispatcherServlet
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.635Z TRACE 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] o.s.web.servlet.DispatcherServlet
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.635Z TRACE 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] o.s.web.servlet.DispatcherServlet
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.635Z TRACE 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] o.s.web.servlet.DispatcherServlet
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.640Z TRACE 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] o.s.web.servlet.DispatcherServlet
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.641Z TRACE 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] o.s.web.servlet.DispatcherServlet
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.643Z DEBUG 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] o.s.web.servlet.DispatcherServlet
nt unsafe logging of potentially sensitive data
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.643Z INFO 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] o.s.web.servlet.DispatcherServlet
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.664Z TRACE 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] o.s.web.servlet.DispatcherServlet
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.687Z TRACE 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] s.w.s.m.m.a.RequestMappingHandlerMappi
ttpServletResponse)
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.718Z TRACE 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] o.s.web.method.HandlerMethod
ctor.ResponseFacade@27e130cb]
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.719Z INFO 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] i.DeviceCapability.DcapManager
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.855Z INFO 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] i.DeviceCapability.DcapManager
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.947Z INFO 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] i.D.DeviceCapabilityService
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.982Z INFO 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] i.DeviceCapability.DcapManager
="urn:ieee:std:2030.5:ns" xmlns:xsi="http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema-instance" href="/dcap">
java-backend   | <TimeLink href="/dcap/tm"/>
java-backend   | <EndDeviceListLink all="1" href="/edev"/>
java-backend   | </DeviceCapability>
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:13.997Z TRACE 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] o.s.web.servlet.DispatcherServlet
ieee2030-server | CURL request successful. Response size: 262
java-backend   | 2025-11-20T00:53:14.007Z DEBUG 1 --- [0.0-8080-exec-1] o.s.web.servlet.DispatcherServlet
java-backend   | Received on [response.client]: <DeviceCapability xmlns="http://ieee.org/2030.5" href="/dcap">
java-backend   | <TimeLink href="/dcap/tm"/>
java-backend   | <EndDeviceListLink all="1" href="/edev"/>
java-backend   | </DeviceCapability>
java-backend   |

```

Figure 21 Device Capability request from the Client (Device)

The server response listed which client is connected and deliver the requested resource which is /dcap in this case, the response is logged since the server is part of the testing system it will receive the message from NATS the NATS message will be the response that the client receives from the server the obtained response will send to the golden standard to validate the response pass the test or not.

6 CONCLUSION

The laboratory tests carried out in 3 different labs in the InterSTORE project shows that the opted interoperability testing scenarios can seamlessly integrate with the diverse laboratory settings. These results depict the versatility and adaptable characteristics of the developed software tools. The Interoperability Testing Methodology proposed by the JRC was chosen as the apt tool to construct the interoperable scenarios. This selection enables executions in different laboratory conditions to maximize the desirable outcome and minimize implementation bottlenecks.

RWTH laboratory is an academic research environment equipped with tools such as RTDS, Opel RT used in the industry. These real-time simulation tools are used in control hardware in the loop experiments where the power grid simulator receives the frequency and impose control actions for validation of frequency services and load shedding use cases. The tests proved that stability of the grid achieved in desirable amount of time which is 333 ms shows that chosen Interoperability profile qualifies the norms of the fast frequency services. Moreover, the harmony among chosen interoperable chain and actors is stand out point is easily proven by the logs from each actor in the chain this makes the formulated experimental set up ability to demonstrate semantic, operational, performance excellency.

HessTech laboratory infrastructure is Industrial grade and follows standards as per norms, the given experiment validates the interoperability scenarios such as functional, performance, semantic reinforced the interoperability is achieved with excellent outcomes not only that but also the conducted in power hardware in the loop promises average round trip communication latency 150-180 ms for dynamic grid services, on top of this outstanding results the stable synchronisation between various actors of the interoperability chain such as BMS ,Converter, EMS is achieved.

Enel X laboratory infrastructure is one of kind in the InterSTORE project with a uniqueness that native IEEE 2030.5 infrastructure supported considered as rare sight in EU level. The testing and validating the native device are extremely challenging given unfamiliarity and lack of resources in EU level. The testing procedure and software tools developed in the WP2.3 validates the conformance of the IEEE 2030.5 on a native device. The tests achieved its outstanding results and is able to conform that both client and server communicate seamlessly within the given infrastructure compares with the golden standards to verify it. It is noticeable that there is no need to extra infrastructure to compliment the tests.

To conclude the tasks, carry out in the laboratories is successful and validates the software tools developed in the WP2 is apt and adoptable to the field pilots of the InterSTORE projects. The key indicators to take away is that the given experimental set up truly achieves interoperability in the RWTH and HessTech Laboratory, the Enel X industrial laboratory witnessed first conformance tests of native IEEE 2030.5 reported in EU. This marks success of InterSTORE project introducing experimental innovation and validation of IEEE 2030.5 protocol and paves way for future research and development and industry adaptation.

7 REFERENCES

Chapter no.	Title	Source(s)
2.1	Introduction to interoperable testing methodology	[1] https://publications.jrc.ec.europa.eu/repository/handle/JRC110455
2.2	Use Case Creation	[2] https://www.mdpi.com/1996-1073/13/7/1648
3.1	Adopted Test bench with LPC in RWTH Laboratory	[3] https://www.ll.mit.edu/r-d/publications/banshee-distribution-network-benchmark-and-prototyping-platform-hardware-loop
3.1.5	VILLAS NODE	[4] https://villas.fein-aachen.org/docs/node/
3.1.6	RTDS Simulator	[5] https://www.rtds.com/
3.1.7	Identification of Interoperability Profiles	[6] https://nats.io/
3.1.7	Identification of Interoperability Profiles	[7] https://mqtt.org/
3.1.7	Identification of Interoperability Profiles	[8] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Web-Socket
3.3	Adopted Test Bench with Testing Tool to Validate IEEE 2030.5 in Enel X Laboratory	[9] https://standards.ieee.org/ieee/2030.5/5897/
3.3	Adopted Test Bench with Testing Tool to Validate IEEE 2030.5 in Enel X Laboratory	[10] https://sunspec.org/ieee-2030-5-csip-certification/

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment

4.1.2	Configuration of To and from of LPC	[11] https://www.docker.com/
4.3.1	Device Configuration	[12] https://solar.se.com/eu/en/product/xw-pro-230v/

8 LIST OF TABLES

Table 1 Step by Step Analysis of Use Case 1	20
Table 2 List of the BAPs considered for the selected UC	22
Table 3 List of some BAIOPs	22
Table 4 List of actors with types	26
Table 5 frequency vs time recorded latency	55
Table 6: KPI analysis for VI test-UC4	58

9 LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1 Block diagram of EC-JRC-SGILP propose methodology for Interoperability test...	13
Figure 2 Test bed set up adopted based on use case in RWTH laboratory	15
Figure 3 Banshee microgrid modelled in RSCAD.....	16
Figure 4 Test bed set up adopted based on use case in RWTH laboratory	17
Figure 5 Energy Management Systems GUI.....	18
Figure 6 Message Sequence chart representing the interaction between the UC actors	19
Figure 7 Message Sequence chart representing the interaction between the UC4 actors ...	25
Figure 8 GTNET-SKT block to set up the outgoing configuration.....	34
Figure 9 VILLAS NODE Configuration	34
Figure 10 Configuration of LPC.....	35
Figure 11 Configuration of EMS to LPC.....	40
Figure 12 Docker Compose with all services listed	42
Figure 13 GUI of the IEEE 2030.5 device	49
Figure 14 Docker compose of the testing tool.....	49
Figure 15 Use Case 4 Innovative frequency service (Load Shedding)	54
Figure 16 Testing Scenario for T3.4– VI (UC4-Innovative Frequency services BESS)	56
Figure 17 Laboratory experimental results of VI service: Frequency at the POC with full time window.....	57
Figure 18 Laboratory experimental results of VI service: Frequency at the POC with zoom at the first frequency event.....	57
Figure 19 Laboratory experimental results of VI service: Output power of storage elements	58
Figure 20 Device Capability request from the Client (Device)	60
Figure 21 Device Capability request from the Client (Device)	61

D3.4 Report on Test and validate on Laboratory Environment